

**Supplementary material. Association of hormonal exposures with grip strength in women
over 45 years: data from the CONSTANCES cohort study**

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Supplementary methods. Multiple imputation

In addition to the covariates included in the main analysis, the final multiple imputation model included proxies of physical performances: self-perceived general health (ordinal variable from 1 "very good" to 8 "very bad"), fast walking speed (in cm/s), ability to stand on one leg for 30 seconds without support (categorical variable: ≥ 30 seconds, 16-29 seconds, less than 16 seconds), and self-reported limitations to perform each of the 3 tasks: carrying an object weighing 5 kilograms over a distance of 10 meters, walking 1 kilometer alone without stopping (with or without a cane) and walking up or down a flight of stairs alone (binary variables: no difficulty, some/a lot of difficulties/unable).

We also considered auxiliary variables related to physical performance, socio-economic characteristic, and health behaviors: falls in the last 12 months (yes, no), orthopedic diseases (yes, no) defined as history of back or knee surgery or history of femoral or vertebral fracture, respiratory diseases, fruit consumption (less, at least once a day), vegetables consumption (less, at least once a day), socio-professional category of the father during the participant's adolescence (farmer, craftsman/trader/business owner, manager/executive/upper intellectual, intermediate profession, employee, manual worker, retired, unemployed), last socio-professional category of the participant, (farmer, craftsman/trader/business owner, manager/executive/upper intellectual, intermediate profession, employee, manual worker, retired, never worked), wearing a visual correction during the vision test (yes, no) and sensory deficit (yes, no) defined as a vision impairment (visual acuity $< 20/40$ in the better eye) or a hearing impairment (≥ 35 dB in the better ear) during the clinical examination at health screening center.

Supplementary Table 1. Associations between participant's characteristics and missing grip strength

Characteristics	Grip strength			
	Not missing	Missing	P *	
N total = 37,976				
N (%)	32,069 (84.4)	5907 (15.6)		
Age (y), M (SD)	57.3 (7.1)	56.4 (7.4)	< 0.01	
Anthropometric characteristics,				
Height (cm), M (SD) (MV=301)	161.9 (6.2)	161.8 (6.3)	0.13	
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SD) (MV=793)	24.9 (4.7)	25.0 (4.9)	0.22	
Childhood silhouette, N (%) (MV=13,822)	Slim	4787 (22.8)	728 (23.1)	
	Normal	12,064 (57.4)	1798 (57.1)	
	Overweight	4153 (19.8)	624 (19.8)	0.56
Silhouette at 18 years, N (%) (MV=13,564)	Slim	5960 (28.0)	895 (28.1)	
	Normal	13,087 (61.7)	1938 (60.8)	
	Overweight	2178 (10.3)	354 (11.1)	0.78
Socioeconomic characteristics, N (%)				
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=2303)	Farmer	3407 (11.2)	494 (9.0)	
	Craftsman/trader/business	4420 (14.7)	853 (15.5)	
	Manager/executive/upper	5698 (18.9)	1254 (22.8)	
	Intermediate profession	4604 (15.3)	850 (15.4)	
	Employee	3238 (10.7)	561 (10.2)	
	Manual worker	8177 (27.1)	1370 (24.9)	
	No occupation / other	624 (2.1)	123 (2.2)	< 0.01
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1354)	Farmer	3006 (9.7)	447 (7.9)	
	Craftsman/trader/business	2487 (8.0)	468 (8.3)	
	Manager/executive/upper	1097 (3.5)	293 (5.2)	
	Intermediate profession	3005 (9.7)	672 (11.9)	
	Employee	5351 (17.3)	1013 (17.9)	
	Manual worker	2320 (7.5)	409 (7.2)	
	No occupation/ other	13,688 (44.3)	2366 (41.6)	< 0.01
Marital status (MV=923)	Couple	19,992 (63.8)	3265 (57.2)	
	Single	4370 (13.9)	1130 (19.8)	
Monthly income (MV=3493)	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	6978 (22.3)	1318 (23.1)	< 0.01
	< 1500€	2953 (10.1)	717 (13.5)	
	1500€ -2800€	8509 (29.2)	1544 (29.1)	
Education (MV=759)	> 2800€	17,721 (60.7)	3039 (57.3)	< 0.01
	No/Primary education	9422 (29.9)	1629 (28.3)	
	High school degree	5524 (17.6)	889 (15.5)	
Heavy physical labor (MV=2608)	Bachelor/More/Others	16,523 (52.5)	3230 (56.2)	< 0.01
		8312 (27.8)	1556 (28.7)	0.17
Health behaviours, N (%)				
Physical activity (MV=1988)	Inactive	6616 (21.7)	1332 (24.0)	
	Moderately active	13,427 (44.1)	2541 (45.9)	
	Very active	10,404 (34.2)	1668 (30.1)	< 0.01
Alcohol (MV=5595)	No consumption	5045 (18.3)	962 (19.7)	
	Moderate consumption	20,199 (73.5)	3487 (71.5)	
	Unsafe consumption	2258 (8.2)	430 (8.8)	0.43
Smoking status (MV=1834)	Ever	14,843 (48.5)	2822 (50.8)	< 0.01

Medical conditions, N (%)

Hypercholesterolemia (MV=109)		11,162 (34.8)	1733 (29.8)	< 0.01
Hypertension (MV=105)		10,351 (32.3)	1743 (30.0)	0.05
Diabetes (MV=99)		985 (3.1)	226 (3.9)	< 0.01
Depressive symptoms (MV=3104)		7832 (26.5)	1645 (30.7)	< 0.01
MMSE score (MV=5241)	≥ 29	17,295 (54.4)	416 (45.7)	
	28	5796 (18.2)	165 (18.1)	
	< 28	8733 (27.4)	330 (36.2)	< 0.01
CVD (MV=799)		545 (1.7)	109 (2.0)	0.08
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1771)		5191 (16.8)	953 (17.8)	< 0.01
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		152 (0.5)	27 (0.5)	0.99
History of breast cancer		1507 (4.7)	253 (4.3)	0.37

Test conditions, N (%)

Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	7047 (22.0)	145 (13.8)	
	Electronic dynamometer	25,022 (78.0)	907 (86.2)	< 0.01
Specific conditions for GS test		5347 (16.7)	-	NA

M, mean; SD, standard deviation; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases.

*adjusted for age

Supplementary Table 2. Associations between characteristics of reproductive history, exogenous hormones use and missing values for grip strength

Hormonal exposures		Grip strength		
		Not missing	Missing	P *
N total = 37,976		32,069 (84.4)	5907 (15.6)	
N (%)				
Characteristics of puberty period				
Age at menarche (y), M (SD) (MV=1856)		13.0 (1.7)	13.1 (1.7)	0.16
Characteristics of reproductive lifespan period				
Nulliparous, N % (MV=583)	Yes	4,231 (13.4)	995 (17.2)	< 0.01
Parity ¹ , N % (MV=7)	1	5137 (18.8)	1100 (23.0)	
	2	13,398 (49.0)	2235 (46.7)	
	≥ 3	8837 (32.2)	1453 (30.3)	< 0.01
Age at first birth ¹ (y), M (SD) (MV=121)		26.8 (4.9)	27.6 (5.5)	<0.01
Breastfeeding ¹ , N % (MV=1304)	Never	7548 (28.7)	1304 (28.4)	0.95
Duration of breastfeeding ^{1,2} (months), N % (MV=402)	[1-5[	5859 (31.8)	964 (30.0)	
	[5-10	6044 (32.9)	1009 (31.3)	
	≥ 10	6488 (35.3)	1245 (38.7)	0.01
Contraceptive pill use, N % (MV=2119)	Ever	27,127 (89.6)	4909 (88.1)	< 0.01
Duration of contraceptive pill use ³ (y), N % (MV=485)	< 1	1284 (4.8)	249 (5.2)	
	[1-5[	5950 (22.3)	1052 (21.8)	
	≥ 5	19,493 (72.9)	3523 (73.0)	0.33
Age at first contraceptive pill initiation ³ (y), M (SD) (MV=1375)		20.6 (4.4)	20.5 (4.4)	0.45
Characteristics of menopausal period				
Menopausal status, N % (MV=908)	Premenopausal	7162 (22.9)	1560 (27.1)	
	Perimenopausal	445 (1.4)	80 (1.4)	
	Postmenopausal	23,706 (75.7)	4115 (71.5)	0.36
Type of menopause ⁴ , N % (MV=276)	Natural	20,212 (86.1)	3565 (87.5)	
	Surgical	2536 (10.8)	382 (9.4)	
	Iatrogenic	723 (3.1)	127 (3.1)	0.04
Age at menopause ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=554)		49.9 (4.9)	49.8 (4.9)	0.39
Reproductive lifetime duration ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=1863)		37.0 (5.1)	36.8 (5.1)	0.33
Time since onset of menopause ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=607)		10.2 (6.7)	10.1 (6.76)	0.28
HT use ⁴ , N % (MV=7610)	Never	10196 (58.9)	1757 (60.3)	
	Past	4720 (27.3)	705 (24.2)	
	Current	2383 (13.8)	450 (15.5)	0.80
Age at current HT initiation ^{4,5} (y), M (SD) (MV=565)		50.9 (5.2)	50.7 (4.9)	0.53

M, mean; SD, standard deviation; MV, missing values before multiple imputation HT, hormone therapy.

¹among parous women; ²among women who ever breastfed; ³among ever users of pill; ⁴among postmenopausal women; ⁵among current users of HT.

*adjusted for age

Supplementary Table 3. General characteristics of the study population before imputation.

Characteristics N = 32,069	Teriles of GS (kg)				
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd		
Maximal grip strength (kg), M (SD)	26.6 (5.8)	20.8 (3.2)	26.5 (1.1)	32.6 (3.7)	
Age (y), M (SD)	57.3 (7.1)	59.2 (6.9)	57.6 (7)	55 (6.7)	
Anthropometric characteristics					
Height (cm), M (SD) (MV=180)	161.9 (6.2)	159.5 (5.9)	161.7 (5.8)	164.4 (5.8)	
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SD) (MV=576)	24.9 (4.7)	25 (4.8)	24.8 (4.6)	25 (4.7)	
Childhood silhouette, N (%) (MV=11,044)	Slim	4795 (22.8)	1862 (25.1)	1387 (22.8)	1546 (20.5)
	Normal	12,074 (57.4)	4120 (55.5)	3511 (57.7)	4443 (59.1)
	Overweight	4156 (19.8)	1436 (19.4)	1188 (19.5)	1532 (20.4)
Silhouette at 18 years, N (%) (MV=10,818)	Slim	5968 (28.0)	2259 (30.1)	1739 (28.2)	1970 (25.9)
	Normal	13,104 (61.7)	4430 (59.1)	3818 (62.0)	4856 (63.9)
	Overweight	2179 (10.3)	807 (10.8)	602 (9.8)	770 (10.2)
Socioeconomic characteristics, N (%)					
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1901)	Farmer	3407 (11.3)	1156 (10.7)	1000 (11.5)	1251 (11.7)
	Craftsman/trader/business	4420 (14.7)	1644 (15.3)	1330 (15.3)	1446 (13.5)
	Manager/executive/upper	5698 (18.9)	1847 (17.2)	1661 (19.2)	2190 (20.4)
	Intermediate profession	4604 (15.3)	1496 (13.9)	1329 (15.3)	1779 (16.6)
	Employee	3238 (10.7)	1181 (11.0)	919 (10.6)	1138 (10.6)
	Manual worker	8177 (27.1)	3214 (29.8)	2265 (26.1)	2698 (25.2)
	No occupation/other	624 (2.0)	231 (2.1)	166 (2.0)	227 (2.0)
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1115)	Farmer	3006 (9.7)	1002 (9.1)	886 (10.0)	1118 (10.2)
	Craftsman/trader/business	2487 (8.0)	926 (8.4)	766 (8.6)	795 (7.2)
	Manager/executive/upper	1097 (3.5)	334 (3.0)	306 (3.5)	457 (4.2)
	Intermediate profession	3005 (9.7)	919 (8.3)	853 (9.6)	1233 (11.2)
	Employee	5351 (17.3)	1809 (16.4)	1482 (16.7)	2060 (18.7)
	Manual worker	2320 (7.5)	945 (8.5)	619 (7.0)	756 (6.9)
	No occupation/other	13,688 (44.3)	5129 (46.3)	3967 (44.6)	4592 (41.7)
Marital status (MV=729)	Couple	19,992 (63.8)	7055 (62.8)	5718 (63.7)	7219 (64.9)
	Single	4370 (13.9)	1534 (13.6)	1204 (13.4)	1632 (14.7)
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	6978 (22.3)	2654 (23.6)	2056 (22.9)	2268 (20.4)
Monthly income (MV=2886)	< €1500	2953 (10.1)	1281 (12.4)	804 (9.6)	868 (8.3)
	€1500€ -2800	8509 (29.2)	3361 (32.4)	2413 (28.8)	2735 (26.2)
	> €2800	17,721 (60.7)	5722 (55.2)	5168 (61.6)	6831 (65.5)
Education (MV=600)	No/Primary education	9422 (29.9)	4064 (36.0)	2675 (29.7)	2683 (24.0)
	High school degree	5524 (17.6)	1991 (17.6)	1570 (17.3)	1963 (17.6)
	Bachelor/More/Others	16,523 (52.5)	5229 (46.4)	4777 (53.0)	6517 (58.4)
Heavy physical labor (MV=2126)	Yes	5347 (16.7)	2544 (22.1)	1391 (15.1)	1412 (12.4)
Health behaviours, N (%)					
Physical activity (MV=1622)	Inactive	6616 (21.7)	2411 (22.3)	1830 (21.0)	2375 (21.8)
	Moderately active	13,427 (44.1)	4691 (43.4)	3834 (44.0)	4902 (44.9)
	Very active	10,404 (34.2)	3712 (34.3)	3054 (35.0)	3638 (33.3)
Alcohol (MV=4567)	No consumption	5045 (18.3)	1944 (20.3)	1435 (18.2)	1666 (16.6)
	Moderate consumption	20,199 (73.5)	6901 (71.9)	5805 (73.6)	7493 (74.8)
	Unsafe consumption	2258 (8.2)	748 (7.8)	653 (8.2)	857 (8.6)
Smoking status (MV=1481)	Ever	14,843 (48.5)	4979 (45.5)	4286 (48.9)	5578 (51.2)

Medical conditions, %

Hypercholesterolemia (MV=14)		11,162 (34.8)	4427 (38.5)	3266 (35.5)	3469 (30.6)
Hypertension (MV=10)		10,351 (32.3)	4038 (35.1)	2955 (32.2)	3358 (29.6)
Diabetes (MV=8)		985 (3.1)	456 (4.0)	257 (2.8)	272 (2.4)
Depressive symptoms (MV=2564)		7832 (26.5)	3084 (29.6)	2138 (25.3)	2610 (24.6)
MMSD score (MV=245)	≥ 29	17,295 (54.4)	5769 (50.6)	4974 (54.6)	6552 (58.0)
	28	5796 (18.2)	2120 (18.5)	1645 (18.1)	2031 (18.0)
	< 28	8733 (27.4)	3523 (30.9)	2494 (27.3)	2716 (24.0)
CVD (MV=396)		545 (1.7)	236 (2.1)	148 (1.6)	161 (1.4)
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1219)		5191 (16.8)	2416 (21.9)	1353 (15.3)	1422 (13.0)
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		152 (0.5)	66 (0.6)	45 (0.5)	41 (0.4)
History of breast cancer		1507 (4.7)	668 (5.8)	412 (4.5)	427 (3.8)

Test conditions, %

Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	7047 (22.0)	3141 (27.3)	1825 (19.9)	2081 (18.3)
	Electronic dynamometer	25,022 (78.0)	8375 (72.7)	7367 (80.1)	9280 (81.7)
Specific conditions for GS test		5347 (16.7)	2544 (22.1)	1391 (15.1)	1412 (12.4)

M, mean; SD, standard deviation; MV, missing values; BMI: body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases.

After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with GS (p-value < 0.01), except hypercholesterolemia, CVD, and history of uterine or ovarian cancer.

Supplementary Table 4. Characteristics of reproductive history and exogenous hormones use of the study population before imputation.

Characteristics		Teriles of GS (kg)			
		1 st	2 nd	3 rd	
N = 32,069					
Characteristics of puberty period					
Age at menarche (y), M (SD) (MV=1519)		13.0 (1.7)	12.9 (1.7)	13.0 (1.6)	13.1 (1.7)
Characteristics of reproductive lifespan period					
Nulliparous, N (%) (MV=459)	Yes	4231 (13.4)	1584 (14.0)	1190 (13.1)	1457 (13.0)
Parity ¹ , N (%) (MV=7)	1	5137 (18.87)	1967 (20.2)	1515 (19.2)	1655 (16.9)
	2	13,398 (49.0)	4736 (48.8)	3857 (48.9)	4805 (49.1)
	≥ 3	8837 (32.3)	3006 (31.0)	2511 (31.9)	3320 (34.0)
Age at first birth ¹ (y), M (SD) (MV=102)		26.8 (4.9)	26.3 (5.0)	26.8 (4.9)	27.3 (4.9)
Breastfeeding ¹ , N (%) (MV=1101)	Never	7548 (28.7)	2989 (32.4)	2180 (28.8)	2379 (25.1)
Duration of breastfeeding ^{1,2} (months), N (%) (MV=339)	[1-5[	5859 (31.9)	2194 (35.9)	1671 (31.5)	1994 (28.6)
	[5-10[	6044 (32.9)	1940 (31.8)	1775 (33.5)	2329 (33.4)
	≥ 10	6488 (35.3)	1973 (32.3)	1856 (35.0)	2659 (38.0)
Contraceptive pill use, N (%) (MV=1876)	Ever	27,127 (89.6)	9355 (87.4)	7855 (90.3)	9917 (91.2)
Duration of contraceptive pill use ³ (y), N (%) (MV=400)	< 1	1284 (4.8)	477 (5.2)	344 (4.5)	463 (4.7)
	[1-5[	5950 (22.3)	2170 (23.6)	1716 (22.2)	2064 (21.1)
	≥ 5	19,493 (72.9)	6540 (71.2)	5676 (73.3)	7277 (74.2)
Age at first contraceptive pill initiation ³ (y), M (SD) (MV=1149)		20.7 (4.4)	21.2 (4.6)	20.6 (4.3)	20.1 (4.2)
Characteristics of menopausal period					
Menopausal status, N (%) (MV=756)	Premenopausal	7162 (22.9)	1603 (14.1)	1882 (21.0)	3677 (33.4)
	Perimenopausal	445 (1.4)	125 (1.1)	132 (1.5)	188 (1.7)
	Postmenopausal	23,706 (75.7)	9610 (84.8)	6961 (77.5)	7135 (64.9)
Type of menopause ⁴ , N (%) (MV=235)	Natural	20,212 (86.1)	8217 (86.4)	5985 (86.7)	6010 (85.1)
	Surgical	2536 (10.8)	991 (10.4)	724 (10.5)	821 (11.6)
	Iatrogenic	723 (3.1)	298 (3.2)	192 (2.8)	233 (3.3)
Age at menopause ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=448)		49.9 (4.9)	50 (4.9)	50 (4.8)	49.7 (4.9)
Reproductive lifetime duration ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=1551)		37 (5.1)	37.1 (5.1)	37.1 (4.9)	36.7 (5.1)
Time since onset of menopause ⁴ (y), M (SD) (MV=493)		10.2 (6.7)	11.2 (6.8)	10.3 (6.5)	8.9 (6.6)
HT use ⁴ , N (%) (MV=6407)	Never	10,196 (58.9)	3868 (55.5)	2987 (59.2)	3341 (63.2)
	Past	4720 (27.3)	2180 (31.3)	1402 (27.8)	1138 (21.5)
	Current	2383 (13.8)	916 (13.2)	656 (13.0)	811 (15.3)
Age at current HT initiation ^{4,5} (y), M (SD) (MV=469)		50.9 (5.3)	50.9 (5.1)	51.1 (5.1)	50.8 (5.5)

M, mean; SD, standard deviation; MV, missing values before multiple imputation HT, hormone therapy.

¹among parous women; ²among women who ever breastfed; ³among ever users of contraceptive pill; ⁴among postmenopausal women; ⁵among current users of HT.

Supplementary Table 5. Associations between participant's characteristics and age at menarche

Characteristics		Age at menarche			
		≤ 12 years	]12; 14[	≥ 14 years	
N total = 37,976					
%		100.0	40.4	23.5	36.1
Age (y), M (SE)		57.2 (0.13)	57.5 (0.14)	56.9 (0.15)	56.9 (0.14)
Anthropometric characteristics					
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=301)		161.6 (0.18)	160.8 (0.18)	161.9 (0.19)	162.4 (0.18)
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=793)		25.0 (0.14)	25.8 (0.14)	24.8 (0.14)	24.3 (0.14)
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=13,822)	Slim	25.6	22.1	25.2	29.6
	Normal	51.7	51.1	53.4	51.3
	Overweight	22.7	26.8	21.4	19.1
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=13,564)	Slim	31.1	27.1	31.2	35.4
	Normal	55.9	57.7	56.8	53.4
	Overweight	13.0	15.2	12.0	11.2
Socioeconomic characteristics, %					
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=2303)	Farmer	11.4	10.5	10.8	12.8
	Craftsman/trader/business	14.7	14.9	14.6	14.6
	Manager/executive/upper	19.2	18.1	21.5	19.0
	Intermediate profession	15.2	15.8	15.9	13.9
	Employee	10.6	11.1	10.3	10.2
	Manual worker	26.8	27.3	25.0	27.4
	No occupation / other	2.1	2.3	1.9	2.1
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1354)	Farmer	9.8	9.2	9.2	10.9
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.2	8.4	7.8	8.3
	Manager/executive/upper	3.9	3.7	4.5	3.7
	Intermediate profession	10.0	10.1	11.1	9.0
	Employee	17.3	18.5	17.0	16.2
	Manual worker	7.5	7.6	7.2	7.8
Marital status (MV=923)	No occupation/ other	43.3	42.5	43.2	44.1
	Couple	62.6	62.7	63.5	62.0
	Single	14.8	14.7	15.0	14.9
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	22.5	22.5	21.5	23.2
Monthly income (MV=3493)	< €1500	10.8	10.7	9.5	11.7
	€1500€ -2800	28.7	29.5	27.1	29.0
	> €2800	60.5	59.8	63.4	59.3
Education (MV=759)	No/Primary education	29.9	29.6	26.9	32.1
	High school degree	17.2	18.1	16.7	16.6
	Bachelor/More/Others	52.9	52.4	56.4	51.3
Heavy physical labor (MV=2608)					
Health behaviours, %					
Physical activity (MV=1988)	Inactive	22.1	22.5	21.4	22.1
	Moderately active	44.3	43.9	44.8	44.5
	Very active	33.6	33.6	33.8	33.4
Alcohol (MV=5595)	No consumption	19.5	20.4	18.7	19.1
	Moderate consumption	72.3	71.8	73.1	72.3
	Unsafe consumption	8.2	7.8	8.3	8.6
Smoking status (MV=1834)	Ever	48.9	48.0	49.4	49.6

Medical conditions, %

Hypercholesterolemia (MV=109)		34.0	35.4	32.8	33.3
Hypertension (MV=105)		31.9	34.3	30.6	30.2
Diabetes (MV=99)		3.2	3.9	2.5	2.9
Depressive symptoms (MV=3104)		27.7	28.3	26.6	27.7
MMSE score (MV=5241)	≥ 29	53.8	53.6	56.3	52.6
	28	18.2	18.5	17.7	18.3
	< 28	27.9	27.9	26.0	29.2
CVD (MV=799)		1.8	1.8	1.7	1.8
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1771)		17.0	18.8	15.7	15.9
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.5	0.5	0.6	0.4
History of breast cancer		4.6	4.7	4.6	4.5

Test conditions, %

Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.7	21.6	21.7	21.8
	Electronic dynamometer	78.3	78.4	78.3	78.2
Specific conditions for GS test		14.1	15.0	13.6	13.3

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases.

After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with age at menarche (p-value < 0.05), except for CVD (p=0.51) and for type of material (p=0.31).

Supplementary Table 6. Associations between participant's characteristics and nulliparity

Characteristics		Nulliparous		
		No	Yes	
N total = 37,976				
%		100.0	85.8	14.2
Age (y), M (SE)		57.2 (0.13)	57.2 (0.1)	56.8 (0.2)
Anthropometric characteristics				
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=301)		161.6 (0.18)	161.7 (0.18)	161.6 (0.20)
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=793)		25.0 (0.14)	25.0 (0.14)	25.0 (0.15)
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=13,822)	Slim	25.6	25.7	25.1
	Normal	51.7	51.8	50.9
	Overweight	22.7	22.5	24.0
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=13,564)	Slim	31.1	31.4	29.3
	Normal	55.9	56.1	54.5
	Overweight	13.0	12.5	16.2
Socioeconomic characteristics, %				
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=2303)	Farmer	11.4	11.6	9.7
	Craftsman/trader/business	14.7	14.7	14.9
	Manager/executive/upper	19.2	18.7	22.4
	Intermediate profession	15.2	15.0	16.0
	Employee	10.6	10.6	10.5
	Manual worker	26.8	27.3	24.0
	No occupation / other	2.1	2.1	2.5
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1354)	Farmer	9.8	10.1	8.1
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.2	8.2	7.7
	Manager/executive/upper	3.9	3.8	4.7
	Intermediate profession	10.0	9.8	11.2
	Employee	17.3	17.2	18.0
	Manual worker	7.5	7.7	6.6
	No occupation/ other	43.3	43.2	43.7
Marital status (MV=923)	Couple	62.7	67.5	33.2
	Single	14.8	8.2	54.9
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	22.5	24.3	11.9
Monthly income (MV=3493)	< €1500	10.8	10.0	15.8
	€1500€ -2800	28.7	27.3	37.1
	> €2800	60.5	62.7	47.1
Education (MV=759)	No/Primary education	29.9	31.3	21.3
	High school degree	17.2	17.4	16.0
	Bachelor/More/Others	52.9	51.3	62.7
Heavy physical labor (MV=2608)		28.2	28.8	24.6
Health behaviours, %				
Physical activity (MV=1988)	Inactive	22.1	21.9	23.5
	Moderately active	44.3	44.0	45.9
	Very active	33.6	34.1	30.6
Alcohol (MV=5595)	No consumption	19.5	19.2	21.3
	Moderate consumption	72.3	72.9	68.7
	Unsafe consumption	8.2	7.9	10.0
Smoking status (MV=1834)	Ever	48.9	48.4	51.7

Medical conditions, %				
Hypercholesterolemia (MV=109)		34.0	34.4	32.2
Hypertension (MV=105)		31.9	32.2	30.3
Diabetes (MV=99)		3.2	3.2	3.3
Depressive symptoms (MV=3104)		27.7	27.4	29.8
MMSE score (MV=5241)	≥ 29	53.9	53.6	55.8
	28	18.2	18.2	18.2
	< 28	27.9	28.2	26.0
CVD (MV=799)		1.8	1.7	1.9
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1771)		17	17.3	15.6
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.5	0.4	0.6
History of breast cancer		4.6	4.6	4.7
Test conditions, %				
Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.7	21.9	20.6
	Electronic dynamometer	78.3	78.1	79.4
Specific conditions for GS test		14.1	14.2	13.6

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases.

After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with nulliparous status (p-value < 0.05), except for height (p=0.08) and for BMI (p=0.82).

Supplementary Table 7. Associations between participant's characteristics and breastfeeding status

Characteristics		Breastfeeding		
		Never	Ever	
N total = 37,976				
%, among parous women		100.0	29.1	70.9
Age (y), M (SE)		57.2 (0.13)	58.0 (0.15)	56.9 (0.14)
Anthropometric characteristics				
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=251)		161.6 (0.19)	161.0 (0.19)	161.9 (0.18)
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=687)		25.0 (0.14)	25.1 (0.14)	25.0 (0.14)
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=11,721)	Slim	25.7	25.4	26.1
	Normal	51.8	53.0	49.0
	Overweight	22.5	21.6	24.9
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=11,504)	Slim	31.4	30.9	32.5
	Normal	56.1	56.8	54.5
	Overweight	12.5	12.3	13.0
Socioeconomic characteristics, %				
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1915)	Farmer	11.6	11.1	13.3
	Craftsman/trader/business	14.7	14.6	14.9
	Manager/executive/upper	18.7	20.8	13.5
	Intermediate profession	15.0	16.0	12.6
	Employee	10.6	10.6	10.5
	Manual worker	27.3	24.9	33.0
	No occupation / other	2.1	2.0	2.2
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1127)	Farmer	10.1	9.3	12.1
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.2	8.1	8.6
	Manager/executive/upper	3.8	4.3	2.5
	Intermediate profession	9.8	10.8	7.3
	Employee	17.2	17.3	17.0
	Manual worker	7.7	6.8	9.8
	No occupation/ other	43.2	43.4	42.7
Marital status (MV=778)	Couple	67.5	67.7	67.4
	Single	8.2	8.1	8.3
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	24.3	24.2	24.3
Monthly income (MV=2938)	< €1500	10.0	10.7	9.7
	€1500€ -2800	27.3	30.9	25.9
	> €2800	62.7	58.4	64.4
Education (MV=626)	No/Primary education	31.3	43.2	26.4
	High school degree	17.4	19.8	16.5
	Bachelor/More/Others	51.3	37	57.1
Heavy physical labor (MV=2182)		28.8	29.7	28.5
Health behaviours, %				
Physical activity (MV=1674)	Inactive	21.9	23.4	21.2
	Moderately active	44.0	42.7	44.6
	Very active	34.1	33.9	34.1
Alcohol (MV=4687)	No consumption	19.2	20	18.9
	Moderate consumption	72.9	72.9	72.9
	Unsafe consumption	7.9	7.1	8.2
Smoking status (MV=1542)	Ever	48.4	48.6	48.0

Medical conditions, %				
Hypercholesterolemia (MV=86)		34.4	37.7	33.0
Hypertension (MV=82)		32.2	35.7	30.8
Diabetes (MV=77)		3.2	3.9	2.9
Depressive symptoms (MV=2602)		27.4	28.4	26.9
MMSE score (MV=203)	≥ 29	53.5	48.5	55.6
	28	18.2	19.8	17.6
	< 28	28.2	31.7	26.8
CVD (MV=697)		1.7	2.2	1.6
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1,491)		17.3	18.3	16.9
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.4	0.6	0.4
History of breast cancer		4.6	5.1	4.4
Test conditions, %				
Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.9	22.7	21.5
	Electronic dynamometer	78.1	77.3	78.5
Specific conditions for GS test		14.2	14.3	14.1

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases. After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with breastfeeding status (p-value < 0.01), except for BMI (p=0.06), smoking status (p=0.26) and silhouette at 18 years (p=0.08)

Supplementary Table 8. Associations between participant's characteristics and contraceptive pill use

Characteristics		Contraceptive pill use			
		Never	Ever		
N total = 37,976					
%		100.0	10.1	89.9	
Age (y), M (SE)		57.2 (0.13)	60.1 (0.17)	56.8 (0.13)	
Anthropometric characteristics					
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=301)		161.6 (0.18)	160.4 (0.21)	161.8 (0.18)	
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=793)		25.0 (0.14)	25.7 (0.15)	24.9 (0.14)	
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=13,822)	Slim	25.6	24.6	25.7	
	Normal	51.7	50.6	51.8	
	Overweight	22.7	24.8	22.5	
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=13,564)	Slim	31.1	28.9	31.3	
	Normal	55.9	55.0	56.0	
	Overweight	13.0	16.1	12.7	
Socioeconomic characteristics, %					
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=2303)	Farmer	11.4	15.5	10.9	
	Craftsman/trader/business	14.7	15.0	14.7	
	Manager/executive/upper	19.2	15.7	19.6	
	Intermediate profession	15.2	11.8	15.5	
	Employee	10.6	10.3	10.6	
	Manual worker	26.8	29.0	26.6	
	No occupation / other	2.1	2.7	2.0	
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1554)	Farmer	9.8	13.3	9.5	
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.2	8.3	8.2	
	Manager/executive/upper	3.9	2.9	4.0	
	Intermediate profession	10.0	7.7	10.2	
	Employee	17.3	12.5	17.8	
	Manual worker	7.5	9.0	7.4	
	No occupation/ other	43.3	46.3	42.9	
Marital status (MV=923)	Couple	62.6	58.8	63.1	
	Single	14.8	19.5	14.3	
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	22.5	21.7	22.6	
Monthly income (MV=3493)	< €1500	10.8	17.8	10.0	
	€1500€ -2800	28.7	34.7	28.1	
	> €2800	60.5	47.5	61.9	
Education (MV=759)	No/Primary education	29.9	40.4	28.7	
	High school degree	17.2	17.3	17.2	
	Bachelor/More/Others	52.9	42.3	54.1	
Heavy physical labor (MV=2608)		28.2	33.2	27.7	
Health behaviours, %					
Physical activity (MV=1988)	Inactive	22.1	22.8	22.0	
	Moderately active	44.3	41.6	44.6	
	Very active	33.6	35.6	33.4	
Alcohol (MV=5595)	No consumption	19.5	26.8	18.7	
	Moderate consumption	72.3	66.0	73.0	
	Unsafe consumption	8.2	7.2	8.3	
Smoking status (MV=1834)		Ever	48.9	32.5	50.7

Medical conditions, %				
Hypercholesterolemia (MV=109)		34.0	40.7	33.3
Hypertension (MV=105)		31.9	39.4	31.1
Diabetes (MV=99)		3.2	5.2	3.0
Depressive symptoms (MV=3104)		27.7	29.6	27.5
MMSE score (MV=5241)	≥ 29	53.8	47.3	54.6
	28	18.2	18.1	18.3
	< 28	27.9	34.6	27.2
CVD (MV=799)		1.8	2.3	1.7
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1771)		17.0	21.3	16.6
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.5	1.0	0.4
History of breast cancer		4.6	5.4	4.5
Test conditions, %				
Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.7	23.7	21.5
	Electronic dynamometer	78.3	76.3	78.5
Specific conditions for GS test		14.1	15.7	13.9

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases. After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with contraceptive pill use (p-value < 0.05), except for father's socio-professional category at adolescence (p=0.39) and history of breast cancer (p=0.25).

Supplementary Table 9. Associations between participant's characteristics and menopausal status

Characteristics		Menopausal status			
		Pre	Peri	Post	
N total = 37,976					
%		100.0	24.3	1.4	74.3
Age (y), M (SE)		57.2 (0.13)	48.7 (0.09)	51.1 (0.24)	60.1 (0.08)
Anthropometric characteristics					
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=301)		161.6 (0.18)	163.3 (0.19)	163.5 (0.32)	161.1 (0.18)
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=793)		25.0 (0.14)	24.6 (0.14)	25.0 (0.25)	25.1 (0.14)
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=13,822)	Slim	25.6	21.4	21.1	27.0
	Normal	51.7	55.1	58.8	50.5
	Overweight	22.7	23.5	20.1	22.5
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=13,564)	Slim	31.1	26.6	29.0	32.6
	Normal	55.9	58.3	60.8	55.0
	Overweight	13.0	15.1	10.2	12.4
Socioeconomic characteristics, %					
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=2303)	Farmer	11.4	8.1	10.2	12.4
	Craftsman/trader/business	14.7	13.9	11.1	15.1
	Manager/executive/upper	19.2	22.6	21.0	18.1
	Intermediate profession	15.2	17.5	14.5	14.4
	Employee	10.6	11.5	13.4	10.2
	Manual worker	26.8	24.1	26.9	27.7
	No occupation / other	2.1	2.3	2.9	2.1
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1554)	Farmer	9.8	6.8	8.5	10.9
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.2	7.5	5.1	8.4
	Manager/executive/upper	3.9	6.0	6.6	3.2
	Intermediate profession	10.0	14.2	13.2	8.5
	Employee	17.3	23.2	21.2	15.3
	Manual worker	7.5	7.0	9.2	7.7
	No occupation/ other	43.3	35.3	36.2	46.0
Marital status (MV=923)	Couple	62.6	62.9	58.4	62.6
	Single	14.8	20.1	20.8	13.0
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	22.5	17.1	20.8	24.4
Monthly income (MV=3493)	< €1500	10.8	9.1	14.9	11.3
	€1500€ -2800	28.7	23.8	24.4	30.4
	> €2800	60.5	67.1	60.7	58.3
Education (MV=759)	No/Primary education	29.9	18.9	24.9	33.6
	High school degree	17.2	15.3	17.1	17.8
	Bachelor/More/Others	52.9	65.8	58.0	48.6
Heavy physical labor (MV=2608)		28.2	27.0	29.5	28.6
Health behaviours, %					
Physical activity (MV=1988)	Inactive	22.1	27.4	25.9	20.3
	Moderately active	44.3	47.9	47.0	43.1
	Very active	33.6	24.8	27.2	36.6
Alcohol (MV=5595)	No consumption	19.5	19.6	22.6	19.4
	Moderate consumption	72.3	73.5	71.0	71.9
	Unsafe consumption	8.2	6.9	6.3	8.6
Smoking status (MV=1834)	Never	51.1	49.7	45.3	51.7
	Ever	48.9	50.3	54.7	48.3

Medical conditions, %

Hypercholesterolemia (MV=109)		34.0	15.1	26.1	40.4
Hypertension (MV=105)		31.9	17.4	21.1	36.9
Diabetes (MV=99)		3.2	1.6	2.0	3.8
Depressive symptoms (MV=3104)		27.7	26.2	34.4	28.1
MMSE score (MV=5241)	≥ 29	53.8	59.6	58.3	51.9
	28	18.2	17.0	16.6	18.7
	< 28	27.9	23.4	25.1	29.4
CVD (MV=799)		1.8	0.7	1.6	2.1
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1771)		17.0	7.6	12.3	20.2
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.5	0.0	0.0	0.6
History of breast cancer		4.6	1.5	4.3	5.7

Test conditions, %

Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.7	21.0	22.6	21.9
	Electronic dynamometer	78.3	79.0	77.4	78.1
Specific conditions for GS test		14.1	7.3	9.6	16.4

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases; Pre, premenopausal; Peri, perimenopausal; Post, postmenopausal; After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with menopausal status (p-value < 0.01), except for height (p=0.06) and for BMI (p=0.43).

Supplementary Table 10. Associations between participant's characteristics and HT use

Characteristics	HT use				
	Never	Past	Current		
% , among postmenopausal women	100.0	59.8	26.3	13.9	
Age (y), M (SE)	60.1 (0.11)	58.9 (0.12)	63.2 (0.13)	59.2 (0.15)	
Anthropometric characteristics					
Height (cm), M (SE) (MV=220)	161.0 (0.19)	161.2 (0.19)	160.4 (0.20)	161.6 (0.22)	
BMI (kg/m ²), M (SE) (MV=574)	25.1 (0.14)	25.4 (0.13)	25.2 (0.14)	23.9 (0.15)	
Childhood silhouette, % (MV=9930)	Slim	27.0	26.2	28.0	28.5
	Normal	50.5	50.1	50.7	51.6
	Overweight	22.5	23.7	21.3	19.9
Silhouette at 18 years, % (MV=9717)	Slim	32.6	31.4	33.7	35.4
	Normal	55.0	55.2	55.0	54.4
	Overweight	12.4	13.4	11.3	10.2
Socioeconomic characteristics, %					
Father's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1706)	Farmer	12.4	12.8	13.1	9.4
	Craftsman/trader/business	15.1	14.8	14.7	17.0
	Manager/executive/upper	18.1	17.5	17.0	22.5
	Intermediate profession	14.4	14.1	14.8	15.4
	Employee	10.2	10.2	10.8	9.1
	Manual worker	27.7	28.7	27.3	24.5
	No occupation / other	2.1	1.9	2.3	2.1
Mother's socio-professional category at adolescence (MV=1010)	Farmer	10.9	11.3	11.3	8.6
	Craftsman/trader/business	8.4	8.3	8.7	8.9
	Manager/executive/upper	3.2	3.1	2.7	4.2
	Intermediate profession	8.5	8.6	8.0	9.3
	Employee	15.3	15.9	13.5	15.9
	Manual worker	7.7	7.7	8.0	6.8
	No occupation/ other	46.0	45.1	47.8	46.3
Marital status (MV=685)	Couple	62.6	62.0	63.8	63.1
	Single	13.0	13.9	10.8	13.5
	Separated/Divorced/Widowed	24.4	24.1	25.5	23.3
Monthly income (MV=2750)	< €1500	11.3	12.2	10.2	9.6
	€1500€ -2800	30.4	31.4	31.5	24.4
	> €2800	58.3	56.4	58.3	66.0
Education (MV=580)	No/Primary education	33.6	34.1	36.1	26.7
	High school degree	17.8	18.2	17.8	16.3
	Bachelor/More/Others	48.6	47.7	46.1	57.1
Heavy physical labor (MV=2218)		28.6	29.9	26.9	26.2
Health behaviours, %					
Physical activity (MV=1666)	Inactive	20.3	22.2	17.1	18.2
	Moderately active	43.1	43.6	42.1	42.6
	Very active	36.6	34.2	40.7	39.2
Alcohol (MV=4297)	No consumption	19.4	20.9	17.9	15.7
	Moderate consumption	71.9	71.2	72.5	74.3
	Unsafe consumption	8.6	7.9	9.6	9.9
Smoking status (MV=1397)	Ever	48.3	48.5	45.9	52.2

Medical conditions, %					
Hypercholesterolemia (MV=79)		40.4	40.2	45.4	31.7
Hypertension (MV=76)		36.9	35.9	43.4	28.9
Diabetes (MV=70)		3.8	4.2	3.9	1.6
Depressive symptoms (MV=2552)		28.1	27.8	29.0	27.4
MMSE score (MV=3579)	≥ 29	51.9	51.5	52.0	53.3
	28	18.7	18.1	19.4	19.7
	< 28	29.4	30.4	28.6	27.1
CVD (MV=588)		2.1	2.1	2.6	1.2
Rheumatological diseases (MV=1323)		20.2	18.0	24.8	20.9
History of uterine or ovarian cancer		0.6	0.7	0.6	0.5
History of breast cancer		5.7	6.7	5.9	0.7

Test conditions, %

Type of material	Hydraulic dynamometer	21.9	19.0	26.9	24.5
	Electronic dynamometer	78.1	81.0	73.1	75.5
Specific conditions for GS test		16.4	15.2	19.2	16.3

M, mean; SE, standard error; MV, missing values before multiple imputation; BMI, body mass index; MMSE, mini-mental state examination; CVD, cardio- and cerebrovascular diseases.

After adjustment for age, all characteristics at baseline were significantly associated with HT use (p-value < 0.01)

Supplementary figure 1. Hierarchical algorithm for definition of menopausal status on study population before imputation

- Premenopausal (n = 8722)
- Perimenopausal (n = 525)